

The following is an English translation of the conference proceedings paper entitled “A New Analysis of Color Illusions Based on the Ambiguity of Shape and Color,” which was presented as a poster at the 68th Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association on September 13, 2004 (Presentation No. 2AM126, p. 510).

The translation has been prepared to remain as faithful as possible to the original Japanese text. Although the original figures were printed in black and white, they have been reproduced in color in this English version.

At the time of the conference presentation, the accompanying paper on neon color spreading in achromatic line segments with chromatic inducing figures was still under review. It was subsequently published in 2005 as:

Sohmiya, S. (2005). Explanation for neon color effect in achromatic line segments on chromatic inducers based on the Multiple Interpretation Hypothesis. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 101, 267–282. <https://doi.org/10.2466/PMS.101.1.267-282>

A New Analysis of Color Illusions Based on the Ambiguity of Shape and Color

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Bressan et al. (1997) reported that when a red target figure is inserted into a magenta inducing figure in a neon configuration, the transparent yellow perceived within the illusory contour is produced by a mixture of the complementary color of magenta (green) and the red color of the target figure. Bressan (1995) further proposed that other neon color configurations follow the general rule:

complementary color of the inducing figure + color of the target figure.

However, Sohmiya (2004) examined thirty combinations of colored target figures and inducing figures in Van Tuijl-type configurations (cyan, magenta, yellow, red, green, and blue) and obtained results that could not be explained by Bressan’s hypothesis.

Method

Neon figures (line width: 0.37 mm; line spacing: 5 mm; visual angle approximately 2°) were printed on white copy paper using an inkjet printer. Seven observers with normal color vision and visual acuity participated.

Reports of illusory colors were obtained using a color-naming procedure (Boynton et al., 1964). The strength of the neon illusion was rated on a four-point scale ranging from absent to strong. Observations were conducted under daylight illumination, and no fixed viewing time was imposed.

Results and Discussion

The following observations contradicted Bressan’s hypothesis.

1 When the target figure was one of the subtractive primary colors (cyan, magenta, or yellow), little complementary color spreading occurred; instead, only the color of the target figure spread.

2 The strongest neon effects were observed not for complementary-color combinations but for: a red target with a blue inducing figure, a green target with a cyan inducing figure, and a cyan target with a green inducing figure.

3 According to Bressan's hypothesis, the complementary color should also be induced within the target figure itself. However, in several configurations the complementary color of the inducing figure was not perceived. Instead, the target figure tended to become assimilated to the color of the inducing figure. In particular, two observers reported perceiving a complete magenta lattice in the configuration consisting of a red target and a magenta inducing figure.

To account for these findings, Sohmiya (2004) proposed the Multiple Interpretation Hypothesis (MI Hypothesis), which explains the neon color effect without assuming complementary-color induction.

The contradiction represented by observation (1) could potentially be accommodated by modifying assumptions regarding the amount of complementary-color induction. In contrast, observations (2) and (3) are difficult to explain merely by adjusting such assumptions.

The basic principle of the MI Hypothesis is that a neon configuration is perceptually ambiguous in both shape and color. The hypothesis is based on the following previous findings:

(a) Colored transparency follows the rules of subtractive color mixing rather than additive color mixing (Beck, 1975).

(b) A neon figure permits both a neon interpretation and a non-neon interpretation, and the neon effect occurs when the former is selected (Van Tuijl & Leeuwenberg, 1979).

(c) The occurrence of neon color spreading requires both the presence of illusory contours and a reduction in pattern strength (Sohmiya & Sohmiya, 1998).

The hypothesis is illustrated using the yellow-neon configuration produced by a red target figure and a magenta inducing figure.

According to condition (a), red can be interpreted as transparent yellow superimposed on magenta. Consequently, this figure permits three principal interpretations (Figure 1).

The CMY interpretation and the RGB interpretation satisfy condition (c) and therefore produce neon color spreading. By contrast, the assimilation interpretation treats the figure as a complete magenta lattice; because no illusory contour is generated, condition (c) is not satisfied and no neon effect occurs.

A further assumption is introduced:

"The color of the neon spreading corresponds to the color assigned to the target figure under the selected interpretation."

Under the CMY interpretation, the target is interpreted as yellow rather than red, and therefore yellow neon spreading is perceived.

Under the RGB interpretation, the target is interpreted as red, producing red neon spreading.

Figure 1 Explanation of the neon effect based on the Multiple Interpretation Hypothesis

However, according to condition (a), the visual system tends to prefer the CMY interpretation over the RGB interpretation. Consequently, the perceived neon color is not a simple mixture of yellow and red, but rather: yellow > red.

Likewise, the target figure itself is perceived as: transparent yellow > red > magenta.

The MI Hypothesis was also effective in explaining the colors of neon effects produced by combinations of colored targets and colored inducing figures (manuscript submitted).

It is furthermore applicable to neon effects observed on black backgrounds. For example, it can explain the blue neon spreading perceived around a white target enclosed by a yellow inducing figure.

The hypothesis can also account for complementary-color induction in simultaneous color contrast. For example, the bluish appearance of a gray disk within a yellow surround may be interpreted as the result of the visual system adopting the interpretation of a transparent blue disk placed on a complete yellow disk (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Explanation of complementary color induction in simultaneous color contrast based on the MI Hypothesis

A limitation of the MI Hypothesis is the lack of direct neurophysiological evidence.

In addition, certain observations obtained with black-background configurations suggest that the relative priority of the CMY and RGB interpretations may differ under those conditions. For example, in some configurations a yellow target shifts toward red when paired with a green inducing figure, whereas it shifts toward green when paired with a red inducing figure. These findings suggest that condition (a) may require modification for black-background stimuli.

Nevertheless, compared with Bressan's hypothesis, the MI Hypothesis provides a superior explanation of the perceived colors in neon color spreading and may also contribute to the explanation of other color illusions. Therefore, the MI Hypothesis deserves further consideration.

Reference

Sohmiya, S. (2004). Explanation for neon color effect of chromatic configurations on the basis of perceptual ambiguity in form and color. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 98, 272–290.

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Note:

The concept introduced in the present study—that perceiving transparency in a two-dimensional figure implies that the visual system unconsciously interprets light as passing through that figure before reaching the retina, and therefore infers that the light source is located behind the figure—was subsequently extended by the author to the interpretation of brightness illusions.

Based on this concept, the author presented a poster entitled “A New Explanation of Brightness Illusions: Unconscious Inference by the Visual System of Light-Source Position and Figure Transparency” at the 69th Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association on September 10, 2005 (Presentation No. 1PM129, p. 516). The presentation proposed that the MI Hypothesis could also account for simultaneous brightness contrast and the White effect within a unified interpretive framework.

As of 2026, the extension of the MI Hypothesis to neon color spreading on black backgrounds remains unpublished.

This note is provided solely to document the subsequent development of the author’s ideas after the 2004 conference presentation. The conference paper itself has not been altered.